

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF MHD FLOW OF MICROPOLAR FLUID WITH VISCOSITY AND THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY EFFECTS

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Abstract: An investigation is done on the effects of variable viscosity and thermal conductivity on MHD flow of micropolar fluid past an inclined plate. The governing PDEs of motion are converted into ODEs with the help of similarity transformations which are then solved numerically for specific boundary conditions using fourth order Runge- Kutta shooting method. Results for the velocity, temperature and micro-rotation profiles are shown by plotting graphs and the values of coefficient of skin friction and Nusselt number are tabulated for different values of the parameters. The effects of variable viscosity and thermal conductivity on the flow are very significant.

Key Words: MHD flow, viscosity, thermal conductivity, shooting method.

Introduction:

Micropolar fluids are viscous non-Newtonian polar fluids with non-symmetrical stress tensor which contain micro-elements that exhibit micro-rotation affecting the flow. Polymeric fluids, colloidal suspensions, drilling mud etc. are some examples of fluid which behaves like micropolar fluid. The micropolar fluid theory is applied in different branches of engineering sciences such as polymer processing, geothermal energy extractions, aerodynamics and fluidics.

The theory of micropolar fluid was first introduced by Eringen [1]. Rashidi *et al.* [2] discussed free convective heat and mass transfer for MHD micropolar fluid flow over a permeable vertical stretching sheet. Olajuwon *et al.* [3] studied the unsteady free convection heat and mass transfer in an MHD micropolar fluid with thermo-diffusion and thermal radiation effects. Numerical solution of MHD flow of micropolar fluid with heat and mass transfer towards a stagnation point on a vertical plate was determined by El-dabe *et al.* [4]. An investigation on MHD mixed convection slip flow over an inclined porous plate with viscous dissipation and Joule heating is carried out by Daset *et al.* [5]. Kim [6] analyzed heat and mass transfer in MHD micropolar flow over a vertical moving a porous plate in a porous medium. Some other authors like Rahman *et al.* [7], Mohanty *et al.* [8], Das [9], Uddin [10], Kaya [11], Singh [12] etc. dealt with the heat and mass transfer of MHD boundary layer flow of micropolar fluid through different medium over different geometrical shapes.

Most of the above mentioned studies are based on constant values of viscosity and thermal conductivity of the fluid. But it is observed that these properties of fluid may vary which affects the flow [13]. So, here, we have planned to study the flow of a micropolar fluid considering the above mentioned properties as variable. The transformed governing equations for the specific boundary conditions are solved numerically using fourth order Runge- Kutta shooting method by developing suitable computer programming code in Matlab.

Mathematical Formulation:

We consider a steady 2D flow of a viscous incompressible micropolar fluid past an inclined plate with an inclination angle α with the vertical direction. Let, (u, v) be the velocity component along (x, y) directions respectively, as shown in the figure. A uniform magnetic field B_0 is applied in the transverse direction of the plate.

Figure 1: Flow configuration

The fluid viscosity and thermal conductivity are assumed to be inverse linear functions of temperature whereas the other properties of the fluid are assumed as constant. Let, N be the micro-rotation component.

Under the boundary layer assumptions, the governing equations are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{\kappa}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{\sigma B_0^2 u}{\rho} + g\beta(T - T_\infty) \cos \alpha - \frac{v}{m^*} (u - U_\infty) \tag{2}$$

$$\rho j \left(u \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} \right) = -\kappa \left(2N + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) + \gamma \frac{\partial^2 N}{\partial y^2} \tag{3}$$

$$\rho C_p \left(u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \lambda \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + (\mu + \kappa) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{\mu}{m^*} u^2 + \sigma (u B_0)^2 \tag{4}$$

Boundary conditions are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = 0, v = 0, T = T_w, C = C_w, N = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \quad \text{at } y = 0 \\ u \rightarrow U_\infty, T \rightarrow T_\infty, C \rightarrow 0, N \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{5}$$

Following Lai and Kulacki [14] the fluid viscosity is assumed as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mu} &= \frac{1}{\mu_\infty} [1 + \delta(T - T_\infty)] \\ \text{Or,} \\ \frac{1}{\mu} &= a(T - T_r) \\ a &= \frac{\delta}{\mu_\infty} \text{ and } T_r = T_\infty - \frac{1}{\delta} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{6}$$

Similarly, the thermal conductivity is considered as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\lambda} &= \frac{1}{\lambda_\infty} [1 + \xi(T - T_\infty)] \\ \text{Or,} \\ \frac{1}{\lambda} &= b(T - T_k) \\ b &= \frac{\xi}{\lambda_\infty} \text{ and } T_k = T_\infty - \frac{1}{\xi} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{7}$$

Let us introduce the following similarity transformations and parameters:

$$u = u_\infty f'(\eta), \eta = y \sqrt{\frac{u_\infty}{\nu_\infty x}}, v = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{u_\infty \nu_\infty}{x}} [\eta f'(\eta) - f(\eta)], \theta = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, N = u_\infty \left(\frac{u_\infty}{\nu_\infty x} \right) g(\eta)$$

Using the above transformations, equation (1) is satisfied identically and the equations (2), (3) and (4) respectively are reduced to:

$$\left(1 + K \frac{\theta_r - \theta}{\theta_r}\right) f'''' = \frac{\theta' f''}{\theta - \theta_r} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_r}\right) f f'' + \left(\frac{Gr}{Re^2} \theta \cos \alpha - \frac{M^2}{Re} f' + K g'\right) \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_r}\right) + \frac{1}{m Re (f' - 1)} \tag{8}$$

$$g'' = \frac{1}{c} (2g + f'') - \frac{1}{2\Delta} (f' g + f g') \tag{9}$$

$$\theta'' = \frac{\theta'^2}{\theta - \theta_k} + \frac{Pr}{2} \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_k}{\theta_k}\right) f \theta' + Pr Ec \left(K - \frac{\theta_r}{\theta - \theta_r}\right) \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_k}{\theta_k}\right) f'^2 - Pr \frac{Ec}{Re} \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_k}{\theta_k}\right) \left(\frac{1}{m} \frac{\theta_r}{\theta - \theta_r} - M^2\right) f'^2 \tag{10}$$

Transformed boundary conditions are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f' = 0, f = 0, \theta = 1, \phi = 1, g = -\frac{1}{2} f'' \text{ at } \eta = 0 \\ f' \rightarrow 1, \theta \rightarrow 0, \phi \rightarrow 1, g \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{11}$$

where, $\theta_r = \frac{T_r - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} = \frac{1}{\delta(T_w - T_\infty)}$ and $\theta_k = \frac{T_k - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} = \frac{1}{\xi(T_w - T_\infty)}$ are dimensionless reference temperature corresponding to viscosity and thermal conductivity respectively. It is to be noted that these values are negative for liquids and positive for gases when $(T_w - T_\infty)$ is positive [14].

Results and Discussions:

The differential equations (8), (9) and (10) with the boundary conditions (11) are solved numerically using the fourth order Runge- Kutta shooting method by developing suitable programming codes in MATLAB. The values of different parameters are taken as $Re = 0.5, M = 0.5, Pr = 0.7, Ec = 0.01, \theta_r = -10, \theta_k = -10, G = 1, \Delta = 0.5, K = 0.01, \alpha = 30, Gr = 2.5$ and $m = 1$, unless otherwise stated.

Fig. 2: Velocity profile for different θ_r

Fig. 3: Velocity profile for different M

The graphical representation of velocity profile u with different values of viscosity parameter θ_r , Hartmann number M , Grashof number Gr and inclination angle α are shown in Figs. 2- 5. It is noticed from the Fig.2 and Fig.3 that when θ_r and M increase, u decreases. As θ_r and M increase, due to the increase of resistive forces, viscous force and Lorentz force the fluid experiences resistance during the flow resulting the decrease of the fluid velocity. Similarly, it is clear from the Fig.5 that when α increases, i.e., the inclination of the plate increases the velocity of the fluid decreases. It is due to the fact that when the inclination angle increases the effect of buoyancy force decreases by a

factor of $\cos \alpha$. In Fig.4, we have seen that increasing values of Gr enhance the fluid velocity. Increase of Gr means the increase of buoyancy force and decrease of viscous force which is the fact for the enhancement of velocity of the fluid.

Fig. 4: Velocity profile for different Gr

Fig. 5: Velocity profile for different α

The effects on temperature profile θ for the variation of θ_r , θ_k and M are shown in Figs.6- 8. The temperature of the fluid enhances with the enhancement of θ_r and M whereas an increase of θ_k reduces the temperature. As the thermal conductivity of the fluid raises heat transfers more from the region of higher temperature to lower temperature, so the temperature of the fluid within the boundary layer diminishes. When θ_r and M boost the flow resistive forces, viscous force and Lorentz force hike due to which the fluid has to do extra work to flow against these forces. This energy of the fluid transforms into thermal energy and as a result temperature of the fluid upsurges.

Fig. 6: Temperature profile for different θ_r

Fig. 7: Temperature profile for different θ_k

Fig. 8: Temperature profile for different M

Fig. 9: Micro-rotation profile for different θ_r

The micro- rotation profiles g for the variation of different parameters are presented in Figs. 9-11. g surges with the increment of θ_r and coupling constant parameter K . Due to the inflation of θ_r temperature of the fluid hikes and then, molecules get released from their bonds holding them. So the rotation of the fluid elements increases.

Fig. 10: Micro-rotation profile for different θ_k Fig. 11: Micro-rotation profile for different K

In Table (1) and Table (2), the missing values $f''(0)$, $g'(0)$, $\theta'(0)$ and the co-efficient of skin- friction C_f and the Nusselt number Nu which represents the wall shear stress and heat transfer rate respectively are expressed. It is noted that the values of $f''(0)$ and Nu upturn with the increment of θ_r and Gr and decline when M and θ_k rise; however C_f drops for the enhancement of θ_r , M and θ_k but boosts with the inflation of Gr . From these tables it is also observed that the values of $g'(0)$ rise and $\theta'(0)$ drops when θ_r , Gr and θ_k enhance.

Table 1

M	θ_r	$f''(0)$	$g'(0)$	$\theta'(0)$	cf	Nu
0.5	-10	1.19844	0.344391	-0.39332	2.190966	0.357564
	-6	1.218082	0.353978	-0.39427	2.100321	0.358427
	-4	1.241385	0.365395	-0.39538	1.99863	0.359433
0.6	-10	1.148916	0.338001	-0.38675	2.100427	0.351586
	-6	1.165945	0.346729	-0.38748	2.010422	0.352256
	-4	1.186032	0.357081	-0.38833	1.909512	0.353026
0.7	-10	1.09706	0.331393	-0.3797	2.005625	0.345185
	-6	1.111503	0.339266	-0.38022	1.916548	0.345658
	-4	1.128426	0.348565	-0.38081	1.816766	0.346189

Table 2

Gr	θ_k	$f''(0)$	$g'(0)$	$\theta'(0)$	cf	Nu
1	-10	1.136769	0.294308	-0.39601	2.07822	0.360011
	-6	1.136246	0.29436	-0.41004	2.077264	0.351463
	-2	1.134019	0.294588	-0.47458	2.073192	0.316384
2	-10	1.244363	0.336566	-0.40277	2.274921	0.36615
	-6	1.242898	0.336436	-0.41699	2.272244	0.357421
	-2	1.236593	0.33584	-0.48239	2.260718	0.321595
3	-10	1.350441	0.378529	-0.4092	2.468852	0.372004
	-6	1.348046	0.378211	-0.42362	2.464474	0.363101
	-2	1.337712	0.376769	-0.48984	2.44558	0.326561

Conclusion:

In this numerical analysis of MHD flow of micropolar fluid, it is found that viscosity and thermal conductivity parameter as well as the other involved parameters have momentous impact on the velocity, temperature and micro-rotation profile. Following are some conclusions drawn from the analysis:

1. Due to the hike of viscosity, velocity of the fluid diminishes and temperature and micro-rotation of the fluid enhances.
2. Increasing values of Hartmann number enhance the temperature but reduce the velocity.
3. Temperature drops when thermal conductivity rise whereas there is no change in micro-rotation with the variation of thermal conductivity.
4. When inclination of the plate increases the velocity of the fluid decreases.
5. Shear stress shrinkages and rate of heat transfer surges with the increment of viscosity whereas both diminishes as the thermal conductivity of the fluid rises.

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Parameters used:

ρ	fluid density	β	coefficient of thermal expansion
μ	coefficient of dynamic viscosity	μ_∞	viscosity at infinity
T	fluid temperature	a and T_∞	constants and their values depend on the reference state and thermal property of the fluid
T_w	temperature of the plate	T_r	transformed reference temperature related to viscosity parameter
T_∞	free stream temperature	δ	constant based on thermal property of the fluid
λ	thermal conductivity	T_k	constants and their values depend on the reference state and thermal properties of the fluid, i.e. on ξ
m^*	coefficient of permeability	$G = \frac{c\gamma}{\kappa v_\infty}$	micro-rotation parameter
j	micro-inertia per unit mass	$K = \frac{\kappa}{\mu_\infty}$	coupling constant parameter
C_p	specific heat at constant pressure	$\Delta = \frac{\gamma}{\mu_\infty j}$	material constant
σ	electrical conductivity	$M = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu_\infty} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} B_0 x$	Hartmann number
γ	spin gradient viscosity	$Pr = \frac{\mu_\infty C_p}{\lambda_\infty}$	Prandtl number
κ	kinematic micro-rotation viscosity	$Ec = \frac{c^2 x^2}{C_p (T_w - T_\infty)}$	Eckert number
g	acceleration due to gravity	$Gr = \frac{g\beta(T_w - T_\infty)x^3}{v_\infty^2}$	Grashof number